

Multi-scale Modelling of a Shell-and-tube Latent Heat Thermal Storage Unit for Building-level Dynamic Simulation

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Abstract:

The optimal management of renewable energy systems can be enhanced by energy storage. Especially, self-consumption of self-produced renewable energy can be maximized. Among the technologies for storing thermal energy, a latent storage system based on Phase Change Materials (PCMs) yields higher energy density compared to a sensible heat storage unit. Thus, Latent Heat Thermal Storage (LHTS) units fit an urban context with building-integrated systems where limited space is generally available. However, the integration of LHTS in an existing or newly developed heating system is hindered by a few technical issues (linked to heat transfer enhancement) and, most importantly, by a scarce knowledge about their dynamic behaviour at system level. Hence, this study presents a multi-scale modelling approach for rapidly simulating the operations of a shell-and-tube LHTS unit. A 1D model for the pipes crossed by the heat transfer fluid (HTF) is coupled with analytical thermal power characteristic curves representing the heat flux exchanged by the PCM domain. In this way, the heat transfer between the PCM and the HTF pipes is decoupled. The adopted thermal power characteristic curves are calibrated on a 2-dimensional model considering different boundary conditions. Summarizing, the proposed model is useful for investigating numerous LHTS building-integrated management strategies thanks to the possibility of varying two relevant input parameters: the HTF mass-flow rate and the HTF inlet temperature.

Keywords:

1D dynamic model; Latent Heat Thermal Storage; LHTS performance characteristic curves; Multi-scale modelling; Phase Change Materials.

Conference topic:

Energy Storage

1. Introduction

The energy consumption of the residential sector in EU represents more than one fourth [1] of the European total final energy consumption. The use of this energy is mainly directed towards heating purposes. Indeed, space and water heating constitute up to 78.4% of the final energy consumption within the EU residential sector [2]. However, the ambitious share of renewable energy set by EU in 2030 requires an increased operational flexibility to the existing household energy systems. Therefore, thermal energy storage is a key element for supporting the flexible operation of existing energy systems. In this context, Latent Heat Thermal Storage (LHTS) technologies represent a promising solution, especially where a limited installation space is available (such as in an urban environment). The heat stored and released through the melting and solidification of Phase Change Materials (PCMs) can reduce the occupied volume up to five times if compared to traditional sensible storage technologies.

Since most of the LHTS concepts require the enhancement of their heat transfer performance, the large majority of the studies found in literature are based on detailed models. In general, computational fluid dynamic (CFD) models are able to describe the local behaviour of the PCM with great accuracy. However, the large degree of detail is paid with a substantial computational effort. A common way to improve the performance of LHTS units is obtained by implementing fins made of high conducting materials (HCMs) on the pipes where the heat transfer fluid (HTF) flows [3]. This type of LHTS concept is generally referred as shell-and-tube. Therefore, numerous modelling approaches have been proposed in the existing literature with the aim of optimizing the LHTS fin design. For example, Niyas et al. [4] analysed a shell-and-tube LHTS with a 3D

numerical model based on a finite element scheme. With the aim of minimizing the total discharging time, they identified the optimal number of pipes with the optimal number of longitudinal fins for a given quantity of PCM. The adopted model was then validated experimentally [5], thus increasing the value of the presented results. A further instance is provided by Sciacovelli et al. [6] who adopted a 2-dimensional cross-section model based on a commercial finite volume code for the optimization of Y-shaped fins. Their results provide an interesting insight on the effect that different fin bifurcations have on the total discharging time and efficiency. An innovative design approach was introduced by Pizzolato et al. [7], who combined a topology optimization technique with dedicated 2D and 3D finite element models. The results provide useful design guidelines for releasing all the LHTS energy content in short time intervals. Another complex model was presented by Esapour et al. [8], who developed a 3D in-house code for a parametric study on the performance of an annular LHTS equipped with a different number of tubes. In a successive work [9], the same authors also investigated the effect of two important operational parameters: the HTF inlet temperature and mass-flow rate. Unlike the above-mentioned studies, only a few articles introduced simpler modelling approaches with a reduced computational effort. For instance, with the aim of improving the geometric and operational parameters of two fin-and-tubes LHTS units, Neumann et al. [10] coupled a 3D model for the PCM and fins with a 1D model for the tubes. The time dependent behaviour of the analysed storage units is accurately predicted, although the PCM properties need a careful calibration and variable operating conditions were not investigated. A different simplification approach was adopted by Parry et al. [11], who proposed a one-dimensional radial model based on an effective thermal diffusivity following the reduction of an experimentally calibrated 3D model. According to the authors, their results predict with good accuracy the LHTS performance over long-time periods. An original lumped model based on the effectiveness-number of transfer units (ϵ -NTU) was suggested by Tay et al. [12]. The proposed semi-empirical correlation was calibrated on a tube-in-tank LHTS and it can be employed for a rapid sizing of the storage unit. Finally, a very interesting modelling approach was introduced by Johnson et al. [13]. This consists of three simplification steps. First, the heat transfer properties of a pre-determined LHTS tube assembly were analysed through a 2D finite volume model. Then a 1D equivalent radial model with an effective thermal conductivity was retrieved. Finally, a 1D axial model for the HTF was coupled to the radial one in Dymola to study the time evolution of the thermal heat flux. However, the authors applied this methodology only for predicting the behaviour of a specific LHTS design under fixed operating conditions and did not investigate variable input parameters.

Nevertheless, although a few articles contextualized the LHTS under study in a broader energy system, the analysis of variable conditions during the LHTS operational phases have received little attention. Fast and accurate dynamic models could give profitable insights on the behaviour of LHTSs at system level. Ultimately, they could favour the optimal integration of LHTS units in energy systems.

In this work, a multi-scale modelling approach is proposed with the aim of predicting the time dependent behaviour of a shell-and-tube LHTS from a system perspective. Hence, a 1D axial model for the HTF pipe is coupled with analytical thermal power characteristic curves for the PCM-HCM assembly. These curves are expressed as a function of the boundary condition (i.e. the temperature at the contact wall between the HTF and the PCM-HCM assembly) and the LHTS current state of charge. Consequently, the proposed modelling approach allows to quickly simulate variable inlet conditions of temperature and mass-flow rate.

2. Methodology

To facilitate the integration of LHTS units in thermal or multi-energy systems, this study proposes a multi-scale modelling approach for rapidly simulating the dynamic behaviour of a shell-and-tube LHTS. This type of storage unit is essentially constituted by two components: the heat transfer fluid (HTF) flowing inside the pipes and the assembly of PCM and high conductive material (HCM) for the pipe shell and fins. Hence, these two domains are modelled separately, and the heat flux exchanged at the contact wall is decoupled. On the one hand, the thermal behaviour of the PCM-HCM assembly is modelled through thermal power characteristic curves calibrated on a detailed 2D cross-section model. On the other hand, the HTF domain is represented through a 1D model along the pipe axial direction. A sketch of the adopted multi-scale modelling approach is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Sketch of the adopted multi-scale modelling approach: 1D time dependent model for the HTF (left) coupled with a mathematical expression for the LHTS discharged thermal power (calibrated on a 2D cross-section model; right)

2.1 Reference 2D cross-section model

The shell-and-tube LHTS taken as a reference for assessing the validity of the estimated thermal power characteristic curves is presented in Fig. 2. This is intended as a repetitive elementary unit for a larger multi-tube LHTS assembly.

Fig. 2. (a) Analysed LHTS shell-and-tube concept; (b) Reduced computational domain

Considering only the discharging phase, the predominant heat transfer mechanism inside the PCM is heat diffusion [14]. Consequently, the computational domain can be reduced to the LHTS horizontal cross-section plane, since here the temperature gradient inside the PCM is expected to be much larger compared to the axial direction [15]. Moreover, the numerical domain can be further reduced exploiting the symmetry created by the fins. The physical problem is modelled using the finite volume method implemented in the commercial code Ansys Fluent (2020 R1). Since natural convection phenomena in the PCM are neglected, the only governing equation is the energy equation, as expressed in Eq. (1). More specifically, the solidification process is modelled and solved through the enthalpy–porosity technique [16].

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho H) - \nabla \cdot (k \nabla T) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where H is the sum of the sensible enthalpy and latent heat of the considered material.

The tube shell is made of copper, while the longitudinal fins are made of aluminium. The PCM properties are reported in Table 1. Perfect contact is assumed between the high conducting materials and the PCM.

Table 1. PCM physical properties

PCM physical property	Value
Density [kg/m ³]	858
Specific Heat [J/(kg·K)]	2300 (solid) 1400 (liquid)
Thermal conductivity [W/(m·K)]	0.2
Latent Heat [J/kg]	224000
Solidus Temperature [°C]	66
Liquidus Temperature [°C]	68

Symmetry boundary conditions are applied on the external faces, while a Dirichlet boundary condition is considered at the internal wall. More specifically, three separate transient simulations were performed with different temperature values imposed at the inner wall: $T_{wall} = 50^\circ\text{C}$, $T_{wall} = 55^\circ\text{C}$ and $T_{wall} = 60^\circ\text{C}$. The numerical model is based on the approach presented by Sciacovelli et al. [6], who adopted a 2D cross-section model for PCM solidification and validated it against experimental data. For further details, the interested reader is referred to [6]. The computational grid is a non-structured triangular mesh made of 4694 cells, which proved to be fine enough not to influence the results. A Second Order Upwind scheme is used for the spatial discretization of the energy equation, while gradients are calculated with the Least Squares Cell Based method. The convergence is reached when residuals are lower than 10^{-9} for the energy equation. Finally, the transient problem is solved with a First Order Implicit Euler method, with a time-step of 1 s. The selected value proved to be sufficiently fine not to influence the results.

2.2 LHTS thermal power characteristic curves for discharging phase

Since LHTS units rely on the change of phase of PCM materials to store thermal energy, their performance is not constant in time. As a matter of fact, the rate at which energy is released or absorbed by these storage units decreases in time. This phenomenon is attributed to the resistive solid/liquid PCM layer that is gradually formed around the HTF pipe and fins as the discharging/charging process advances. Therefore, when fixed boundary conditions are imposed, the thermal power released/absorbed by a LHTS unit at a given time instant depends only on the advancement of the discharging/charging process at that instant. For this reason, it is deduced that the dynamic performance of a LHTS unit with specific boundary conditions can be described through a family of *characteristic curves* that relate the LHTS thermal power to the LHTS state of charge (SOC). The derivation of this family of functions is presented hereafter.

Considering the discharging phase, the energy that a LHTS unit releases in time (E_d) varies between zero and a maximum value. This quantity coincides with the amount of energy stored inside the LHTS at the beginning of the discharging process (ΔE_{tot}). It was observed that the evolution of the discharged energy in time normalized with respect to the LHTS energy content ($E_{d,n}$) is a monotonically increasing function between 0 and 1 whose slope decreases in time. This can be well-described through the mathematical expression reported in Eq. (2).

$$E_{d,n}(t) = \frac{E_d(t)}{\Delta E_{tot}} = 1 - e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\tau_0}\right)^\beta} \quad (2)$$

This expression is also known as the cumulative function for the Weibull distribution and it is characterised by only two parameters: the scale factor (τ_0) and the shape factor (β). The thermal power $q(t)$ ceased by the LHTS at each time instant corresponds to the time derivative of the LHTS discharged energy. Hence, the evolution of the LHTS thermal power $q(t)$ is also dependent on τ_0 and β , as shown by Eq. (3).

$$q(t) = \Delta E_{tot} \frac{dE_{d,n}(t)}{dt} = \Delta E_{tot} \frac{\beta}{\tau_0} \left(\frac{t}{\tau_0}\right)^{\beta-1} e^{-\left(\frac{t}{\tau_0}\right)^\beta} \quad (3)$$

In this framework, the scale factor τ_0 is a time constant indicating the time needed by the LHTS unit to release 63.2% of its energy content. Therefore, this constant is an index for the LHTS speed of discharge: the lower the value of τ_0 , the faster the discharging process. More specifically, the scale factor τ_0 can be expected to be dependent on the boundary conditions at which the LHTS is operated. For instance, assuming that the inner wall of the HTF pipe is kept at a constant temperature T_{wall} for the whole discharging process, the speed of discharge increases as T_{wall} decreases because of the higher temperature difference between the wall and the PCM phase change temperature (T_{pc}). Hence, τ_0 can be expressed as a function of T_{wall} when evaluating the terms of Eq. (4).

$$E_{d,n}(\tau_0) = \frac{E_d(\tau_0)}{\Delta E_{tot}} = 0,632 \quad (4)$$

The total energy stored in the LHTS is approximated by the sensible and latent energy content of the PCM between the initial temperature (T_0) and minimum temperature (T_{wall}), as shown by Eq. (5).

$$\Delta E_{tot} = \rho_{PCM} V_{PCM} \cdot \left[\int_{T_{wall}}^{T_0} c_{p,PCM} dT + \Delta h_{lat} \right] \quad (5)$$

The energy discharged after the time interval τ_0 can be estimated through an average thermal power (\bar{q}), as shown in Eq. (6). In the discharging phase, the heat is mainly transferred by conduction and the PCM thermal resistance is predominant compared to the one of the HCM. Hence, the average heat flux is approximated by the conductive heat flux across a PCM layer of thickness $s_{PCM}/2$, where s_{PCM} is an estimate for the average PCM thickness in contact with the LHTS fins (calculated as $s_{PCM} = V_{PCM}/A$). As far as the average driving temperature difference is concerned, T_{wall} is assumed to be fixed in time, while the average PCM temperature is assumed to be coincident with $T_{pc} = (T_{sol} + T_{liq})/2$ due to the low speed of the solidification process. Thus, only half of the PCM resistive layer is considered in this expression because T_{pc} is assumed to be located at a distance from the wall equal to $s_{PCM}/2$. The contact surface between the PCM and the fins is instead expressed by A .

$$E_d(\tau_0) = \bar{q} \cdot \tau_0 \cong \frac{k_{PCM}}{s_{PCM}/2} \cdot A \cdot (T_{pc} - T_{wall}) \cdot \tau_0 \quad (6)$$

Therefore, the time constant τ_0 can be estimated through Eq. (7), obtained substituting Eq. (5)-(6) into Eq. (4).

$$\tau_0 \cong 0,632 \frac{\rho_{PCM} \cdot s_{PCM}^2 \cdot \left[\int_{T_{wall}}^{T_0} c_{p,PCM} dT + \Delta h_{lat} \right]}{2 \cdot k_{PCM} \cdot (T_{pc} - T_{wall})} \quad (7)$$

As far as the shape factor β is concerned, a value lower than or equal to 1 is expected because it guarantees a monotonic decreasing behaviour in time for the discharged thermal power. Therefore, an optimal value is determined comparing the estimated thermal power evolution $q(t, \tau_0, \beta)$ with the one calculated by the 2D cross-section model $q^*(t)$. The optimal value for β is the one that minimizes the average root mean square error (\overline{RMSE}) considering three different boundary conditions ($T_{wall} = 50^\circ\text{C}$, $T_{wall} = 55^\circ\text{C}$ and $T_{wall} = 60^\circ\text{C}$), as shown in Eq. (8).

$$\overline{RMSE} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{i=1}^3 \sqrt{\frac{\sum [q_i^2(t, \tau_0, \beta) - q_i^{*2}(t)]}{N_i}} \quad (8)$$

Where N_i is the number of points considered in the i -th case. As a result, the optimal value for β is 0.69, which minimizes the average RMSE (27.2 W/m) limiting also the maximum RMSE (31.3 W/m) as highlighted by Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Average and maximum RMSE with respect to the thermal power calculated with 2D model for different values of coefficient β

2.3 Model for the HTF domain

The thermal model for the HTF flowing inside the LHTS pipe is here presented. Considering that the relevant direction is the axial one, a 1D model along the z axis is adopted. Moreover, taking into account the thermal properties of the HTF fluid (water in this case), heat conduction in the axial direction is negligible with respect to mass transport. Indeed, for the most common operating conditions, the velocity of the HTF (u) is such that $u \cdot L / \alpha_{HTF} \gg 1$ (where α_{HTF} is the thermal diffusivity of water and L is the length of the pipe). Hence, the temperature of the HTF along the axis of the pipe at each time instant is modelled through a 1D pure advection problem, as shown in Eq. (9).

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} = \frac{1}{\rho_{HTF} c_{p,HTF}} q''' \quad (9)$$

Temperature and velocity at the tube inlet are fixed at each time instant, while a Robin boundary condition is imposed at the pipe outlet ($\frac{\partial T}{\partial z} |_{z=L} = 0$). The solution is retrieved through a finite volume approach. This guarantees that the energy is conserved in each section of the pipe, allowing for the calculation of the volumetric heat generation (q''') through the thermal power generated by the LHTS when a specific wall temperature (T_{wall}) is reached at the contact wall (see Eq. (10)).

$$q'''(z) = \frac{q_{LHTS}(T_{wall}(z), SOC(z))}{A_{tube} \Delta z} \quad (10)$$

The correct wall temperature is estimated iteratively comparing the value of the thermal power generated by the LHTS at a specific T_{wall} (using the power characteristic curves described in section 2.2) with the one calculated through a global heat transfer coefficient (h_{conv}), as expressed by Eq. (11).

$$q_{LHTS}(T_{wall}(z), SOC(z)) = h_{conv} \cdot A \cdot [T(z) - T_{wall}(z)] \quad (11)$$

Where h_{conv} is evaluated using the Nusselt non-dimensional number, which is in turn estimated by means of the Dittus-Boelter correlation [17].

The advective heat flux between two consecutive cells is calculated with an upwind differencing scheme, while the time formulation is implicit. The space discretization interval Δz is set to 0.001 m, while the adopted time-

step is 1 s. Both of them proved to yield results that are independent on the spatial and temporal discretization schemes.

3. Results and discussion

To rapidly simulate the discharging phase of a shell-and-tube LHTS, this study proposes a multi-scale modelling approach where the heat transfer between the PCM-HCM assembly and the flowing HTF is decoupled. In this framework, the performance of the LHTS is modelled through a family of curves that express the LHTS discharge power as a function of two parameters: the LHTS state of charge (SOC) and the boundary condition at which the LHTS is operated (T_{wall}). On the contrary, the axial temperature evolution of the HTF flowing in the LHTS pipes is estimated through a 1D pure advective model, where the volumetric heat generation coincides with the heat coming from the PCM-HCM assembly at the established T_{wall} . In order to assess the validity of the proposed LHTS characteristic curves, this section first compares their results with the ones obtained from the detailed 2D cross-section model (section 3.1). Then, these power characteristic curves are coupled with the 1D model for the HTF. Thus, the dynamic behaviour of the LHTS is presented from a system perspective (section 3.2).

3.1 Thermal power characteristic curves

Fig. 4 reports the LHTS discharge thermal power calculated through Eq. (3). This compares remarkably well with the thermal power computed by a much more complex 2D simulation with Ansys Fluent. The power curves are presented as a function of the LHTS state of charge (SOC), as defined in Eq. (12).

$$SOC = \frac{E_{LHTS}(t) - E_{min}}{E_{max} - E_{min}} \quad (12)$$

Where: E_{LHTS} is the energy contained in the storage unit at time t ; E_{min} is the minimum energy content that can be reached by the storage unit (i.e. when the LHTS is in equilibrium with the imposed temperature at the wall); E_{max} is the maximum energy content (i.e. the fully charged initial condition).

As expected, a higher power can be extracted from the LHTS for lower wall temperatures due to the larger driving temperature difference that is established with the PCM phase change temperature (67 °C in this case). Indeed, this is confirmed by several studies [18], [19]. Fig. 4 also demonstrates how the calculation of τ_0 through Eq. (7) allows to discern among different boundary conditions with noticeable accuracy. In particular, the description of the thermal power evolution with the presented characteristic curves matches very well the 2D results even in the region where the curves are rapidly changing. This supports the hypothesis that the physical meaning of τ_0 is captured correctly. For further details, the root mean square errors for each of the three cases are presented in detail in Table 2.

A relevant advantage of the proposed methodology for the evaluation of the LHTS thermal power characteristic curves resides in the fact that the discharged energy is conserved. As already mentioned, Eq. (3) coincides with the general Weibull probability density function. Hence, its time integral (corresponding to the discharged energy) will be equal to the total energy stored inside the LHTS for $t \rightarrow \infty$. However, in practice there exists a finite time instant t at which the discharged energy is almost equal to the total energy that was initially stored inside the LHTS. As can be seen in Fig. 5, the evolution of the normalized discharged energy (calculated with Eq. (2)) follows the 2D results satisfactorily, although the discrepancy is higher compared to the simulations of the thermal power, as witnessed by Table 2. This is due to the fact that the coefficient β is calibrated considering the thermal power curves (i.e. the time derivative of the discharged energy function). In fact, in order to minimize the error on the normalized energy curves, β should be chosen equal to 0.89. Nevertheless, the results on the discharged energy appear to be acceptable even when $\beta=0.69$, as the discrepancy after discharging 80% of the initial energy content is lower than 0.05. Moreover, considering the low thermal power supplied by the LHTS when $SOC < 0.2$ (see Fig. 4), in practice the discharging phase could be terminated before reaching $SOC = 0$. For these reasons, the presented model is deemed suitable for quantifying the heat provided by the studied shell-and-tube LHTS from a systemic perspective.

Table 2. Average RMSE on thermal power and normalized discharged energy for different boundary conditions (comparison with 2D model results)

	$T_{wall} = 50^{\circ}C$	$T_{wall} = 55^{\circ}C$	$T_{wall} = 60^{\circ}C$
Thermal power	31.3 [W/m]	26.2 [W/m]	24.1 [W/m]
Normalized discharged energy	0.046 [-]	0.050 [-]	0.064 [-]

Fig. 4. LHTS thermal power characteristic curves for different boundary conditions during discharging phase (comparison with 2D model results)

Fig. 5. Evolution of normalized discharged energy in time calculated with the proposed analytical model and the 2D cross-section model

3.2 LHTS dynamic simulation

As previously mentioned, the multi-scale modelling approach proposed in this study allows to describe the dynamic behaviour of a shell-and-tube LHTS from an energy system perspective. In this context, relevant quantities are:

- the HTF temperatures entering (T_{in}) and exiting (T_{out}) the LHTS unit
- the HTF mass-flow rate (G)
- the overall thermal power released by the LHTS unit.

Two typical case studies are introduced hereafter to show the results that could be achieved coupling the estimated LHTS power characteristic curves with the 1D model for the HTF tube. In the former case the user thermal demand is supposed to be entirely covered by a LHTS unit alone, while in the latter case it is supplied by a LHTS unit in parallel with another technology (such as a classic boiler or district heating). In both cases the user thermal power demand is assumed to be constant, while the HTF inlet temperature and mass-flow rate are regulated depending on the LHTS performance. In order to achieve a description that is independent on the LHTS size and the user thermal demand, the results are presented for a single HTF pipe (whose length is 1.5 m). These can be thus rescaled for a wide range of LHTS sizes assuming that the storage unit is composed of parallel HTF pipes.

Fig. 6 illustrates the evolution of the calculated T_{out} when a LHTS unit is operated as a stand-alone technology with a constant water mass-flow rate (0.05 kg/s per tube). In this case, in order to satisfy the constant user thermal demand, the water inlet temperature must be regulated in a way that the temperature difference between inlet and outlet is kept to a fixed value (3°C in this example). It is interesting to notice the rapid decrease of the produced hot water temperature because of the growing difficulty to extract heat from the storage. Indeed, after 27.8 minutes the discharging process cannot produce hot water at a temperature above 45°C when the HTF mass-flow rate is 0.05 kg/s per tube. If the mass-flow is further increased, this temperature threshold is reached much sooner (15.6 min for 0.075 kg/s per tube and 9.6 min for 0.1 kg/s per tube). This behaviour might be particularly inconvenient for those heating systems requiring higher and more stable operating temperatures. Moreover, the LHTS energy content cannot be fully exploited.

Fig. 6. HTF outlet temperature evolution consequent to a variable HTF inlet temperature and constant mass-flow rate

In the second case study, the LHTS unit is supposed to be operated in parallel with a programmable heating technology. Results are shown in Fig. 7. Unlike the previous situation, the LHTS inlet temperature is constant in time as it coincides with the user return temperature. Moreover, the mass-flow rate passing through the LHTS pipes is controlled proportionally to the temperature difference that the storage unit is able to guarantee (Eq. (13)).

$$G = G_{nom} \frac{T_{out} - T_{in}}{\Delta T_{user}} \quad (13)$$

Where G_{nom} is the nominal mass-flow rate per tube (assumed to be 0.1 kg/s) and ΔT_{user} is the temperature difference requested by the user (assumed to be 5°C).

The water outlet is again rapidly decreasing in time due to the operating nature of the LHTS. Consequently, the mass-flow rate per tube is maximal at the beginning of the discharging process, while it is reduced down to 0.02 kg/s after 1 hour. As this happens, a growing thermal power is demanded to the complementary heating technology in order to satisfy the supply temperature requested by the user (55°C in this example). Therefore, this behaviour suggests the necessity of combining the LHTS technology with a heating technology that is easily controllable for better satisfying the user needs.

Fig. 7. HTF outlet temperature evolution consequent to a constant HTF inlet temperature and variable mass-flow rate

Overall, the presented simulations were implemented in the commercial software Matlab® (R2020a) and run on an 8-core CPU (*Intel i7-9700 CPU @ 3.00 GHz, 16 GB RAM*). The computational time for the two cases amounted to: 12.3 s and 30.9 s. This constitutes a substantial advantage with respect to a full 3-dimensional CFD simulation, whose computational time would be remarkably larger.

4. Conclusions

In this study, a multi-scale modelling approach for simulating the dynamic behaviour of a shell-and-tube LHTS is presented. Only the discharging phase is considered. The storage unit is subdivided into two domains (the HTF and the PCM-HCM assembly) that exchange thermal energy with one another across a contact wall. From an energy system perspective, the HTF flowing inside the LHTS pipes can be easily represented by a 1D pure advective model. However, the thermal power that the HTF receives from the PCM-HCM assembly depends on the state of charge of the storage unit and, more importantly, on the temperature that is established at the contact wall. As a matter of fact, this temperature constitutes a boundary condition for the PCM-HCM assembly of the storage unit. Therefore, an innovative mathematical approach is illustrated in this article in order to estimate the thermal power ceased by the PCM-HCM assembly as a function of its boundary condition (i.e. the wall temperature) and its state of charge. Hence, a family of thermal power characteristic curves is extracted for the considered LHTS unit considering different wall temperature levels (50°C, 55°C and 60°C). These analytical curves compare significantly well with the time evolution of the LHTS thermal power and energy content calculated through a 2D cross-section model in Ansys Fluent. More specifically, the average RMSE on the thermal power curves is limited to 27.2 W/m and the one on the normalized discharged energy curves is 5.3%. Consequently, the 1D model for the flowing HTF is easily coupled with the LHTS thermal power

characteristic curves describing the correct amount of power transferred from the storage unit to the heating fluid. As a result, the dynamic behaviour of the LHTS unit can be quickly examined from a system perspective, since the input HTF temperature and mass-flow rate can be readily modified in time. Furthermore, the limited computational effort constitutes a remarkable advantage. However, it should be mentioned that a model benchmark is currently missing. Therefore, future work should verify if similar dynamic results are achieved by a full 3-dimensional CFD model and, ultimately, in real case studies.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the European commission for funding the H2020-project “RE-Cognition” (project ID 815301).

Nomenclature

A	contact area, m^2
c_p	specific heat, $J/(kg\ K)$
E	energy content, J
G	mass-flow rate, kg/s
H	enthalpy, J/kg
h_{conv}	global heat transfer coefficient, $W/(m^2\ K)$
k	thermal conductivity, $W/(m\ K)$
L	pipe length, m
q	thermal power, W
q'''	volumetric heat generation, W/m^3
s	layer thickness, m
T	temperature, $^{\circ}C$
u	velocity, m/s
V	volume, m^3

Greek symbols

α	thermal diffusivity, m^2/s
β	shape factor, -
ρ	density, kg/m^3
τ_0	characteristic time constant, s

Subscripts

0	initial
d	discharge
lat	latent
n	normalized
nom	nominal
pc	phase change
tot	total

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